

Discordianisme: Grap of Geloof?

ODD# II/2,xii;69Msr0610

Levensbeschouwing, B5VC 2021-2022

Door: Merijn Vervoorn, Rianne Griffioen en Suzanne Nazaripour

Onder het Fnord van: Werner van Rossum (ROW)

Woordaantal: 2616 woorden

00001

Inhoudsopgave

Inhoudsopgave	00001
Inleiding	00002
Wereldbeeld	00003
Organisatie	00004
Individu	00005
Slotvraag: Waarom zijn er religies?	00008
Nawoord	00009
Bibliografie	00010
Bijlage 1	00011

I TELL YOU : ONE MUST
STILL HAVE CHAOS IN ONE
TO GIVE BIRTH TO A
DANCING STAR !
-Nietzsche

THE SACRED

CHAO

6-7-19

Inleiding

Discordianisme is een religie die is gebaseerd op chaos. Hierbij aanbidden zij Eris, de godin van de verwarring. In het komende onderzoek wordt Discordianisme onder de loep genomen. We gaan het hebben over het wereldbeeld, de organisatie en het gevoel dat een individu heeft bij deze religie.

Onder het wereldbeeld vallen de wortels van het geloof, hoe Discordianen kijken naar het leven na de dood, en wat de Erisianen zien als hun doel op aarde.

In de organisatie duiken we de diepte in over hoe het geloof is ontstaan en hoe ze dit in de praktijk brengen. Bijvoorbeeld het bestaan van ontmoetingen en hoe deze eruit zien als ze er zijn. In het hoofdstuk 'Individu' gaan we kijken naar wie Discordianen daadwerkelijk zijn, en wat zij als persoon denken. We doen dit via een online interview.

Wereldbeeld

Discordianisme is een polytheïstische godsdienst. Ze vereren de Godin van 'twist en tweedracht', Eris, ook wel Discordia genoemd. Andere Goden komen ook voor in het heilig boek Principia Discordia zoals de Godin van harmonie, Aneris, ookwel Harmonia genoemd. Er wordt geloofd dat deze Goden invloed hebben op je dagelijkse leven, Discordianen vertellen soms hoe Eris Haarzelf hen een teken heeft gegeven, en dat ze zo tot geloof zijn gekomen.

Discordianen geloven dat het doel van de mens is om Eris te vereren door verwarring te zaaien. Eris lost al jouw problemen op, en in ruil daarvoor los jij die van haar op. Ze geloven dat Eris de heerser van het Materiële Universum is. Ze zou het gewonnen hebben in een scheidingszaak met God tijdens het Voorleven, met de Franse anarchist Pierre Joseph Proudhon als haar advocaat. Niemand is Haar Profeet, en hotdog broodjes eten is een zonde. Al het andere ligt aan het geweten van het individu. Belangrijk is dat verwarring zaaien en een klootzak zijn niet hetzelfde is, sterker nog het tweede zijn verdoemd je.

Eris woont in Limbo, sinds Olympus de toeristische route op is gegaan. Mensen kunnen niet naar het feest in Limbo gaan, aangezien dat gereserveerd is voor Goden alleen. Na het leven op aarde kunnen mensen naar Vahallah (niet Valhalla) gaan, de Regio van Plof (de Christenen noemen dit het Paradijs) en Hell. Maar Hell is alleen gereserveerd voor mensen die Eris ziet als personen die express moeite stoppen in een klootzak zijn tijdens hun verblijf op aarde. Hell is ook niet zo erg als je zou denken, aldus de Principia Discordia. Dode politieagenten (en Gurdjieffianen (volgers van filosoof George Gurdjieff) die zijn vergeten zichzelf te herinneren) worden naar de maan gestuurd, onder leiding van aliens. Er zijn daar twee keer zoveel wetten als op aarde.

Belangrijke mensen in de geschiedenis van Discordianisme zijn Robert Anton Wilson en Bob Shea, de twee schrijvers van de Discordia Practica. Robert Anton Shae had een acid trip flashback in ene bowlinghall, waar hij Eris leerde kennen en daarom de Principia Discordia schreef. Deze acid trip heeft de basis gelegd voor het Discordianisme en is dus een belangrijke gebeurtenis. Bob Shea heeft het geco-schreven.

Organisatie

De religie Discordianisme is opgericht door Greg Hill en Kerry Wendell Thorney. Ze hebben elkaar in 1956 ontmoet op een middelbare school in East Whittier. Greg Hill en Kerry Wendell Thorney hadden nog twee vrienden waar ze veel mee om gingen en met zijn vieren waren ze gek op sciencefiction, radicale politiek en het tijdschrift MAD. Ze gingen in 1957 een keertje naar de bowlingbaan. Ze kregen daar ineens de Heilige Chao te zien kregen door een chimpansee. Dit symbool is een symbool van de godin Eris. Zij was de god van de chaos en verwarring. Eris zei dat haar bewustzijn ooit de mens verlaten heeft en dat ze terugkwam om de mens toch wilde

ontwikkelen. Ze vertelde de vrienden ook dat zij 'chaos' was en dat ze leeft. In 1965 hebben Greg Hill (zijn pseudoniem was Malaclypse the Younger) en Kerry Wendell Thorney (zijn pseudoniem was Omar Khayyam Ravenhurst) het boek "Principia Discordia" uitgebracht. Dit boek wordt gezien als het heilige boek van het Discordianisme. Principia Discordia wekt de indruk dat het Discordianisme is ontstaan als een tegenhanger van de populaire religies. Je kunt dit onder andere herkennen aan het feit dat veel populaire religies orde, structuur en regeltjes belangrijk vinden, echter gaat Discordianisme over chaos en hebben ze slechts één regel; geen regels. Principia Discordia beschrijft dus ook vooral chaos. Het doel daarvan zou zijn om meer evenwicht in de geordende samenleving te brengen. Chaos zou mensen helpen met hoe ze om moeten gaan met de vervelende dingen uit het leven.

Eris is dus de godin van de verwarring/chaos. Zij is de god die vereerd wordt bij het Discordianisme. Haar belangrijkste idee is dat alle orde in de wereld slechts een illusie is. Daarnaast zegt ze tegen iedere luisteraar wat anders en spreekt ze zichzelf ook vaak tegen. Het Discordianisme wordt gezien als een sekte met Episkoposes als leiders van de sektes. De leiders mogen hun titel helemaal zelf kiezen en ze hoeven er geen uitleg over te kunnen geven. De meeste leiders hebben dus vreemde namen aangenomen. De leiders spreken tot Eris door de pijnappelklier. Dit is ook wel de amygdala en dat is het emotionele deel van het brein.

Om lid te worden hoef je niet veel te doen. Iedereen op aarde is een paus. In het boek is er een "pauškaart", die kan je uitdelen aan wie dan ook. Met die kaart maak je iemand geen paus (iedereen is er al één), maar je informeert diegene dat hij een paus is van Discordia. Alleen een paus kan iemand heilig verklaren, maar iedereen is dus al een paus. Hier zie je ook weer de verwarring in terug.

Binnen het Discordianisme zijn er vijf klassen van heiligen. De eerste klasse (de Saint Second Class) gaat over echte mensen, dood of levend. De andere klassen bestaan alleen uit fictieve wezens, omdat die beter zouden zijn om discordianistische perfectie te bereiken. Leden van het Discordianisme spreken elkaar met name online. Er zijn meerdere online pagina's te vinden op bijvoorbeeld reddit. The Discordian Reddit heeft 8,800 leden. Het Discordianisme groeit net zo hard als de wereldbevolking. Er is geen specifieke plaats waar mensen bij elkaar komen. Daarnaast is er ook niet één baas, maar er zijn wel een paar Episkoposes en verder is iedereen een Discordiaanse paus. Eigenlijk is iedereen de baas, of niemand is een baas. Dit past weer in het idee van wanorde en chaos van het Discordianisme.

Deze beweringen worden ondersteund door onderzoeken van Cusack (2013) en Narizny (2009).

Individu

Hoe is het nou voor het individu om zich bij deze godsdienst te voegen? Dat is in dit onderzoek gevraagd aan aanhangers van het Discordianisme. Via Reddit, de voorpagina van het internet, de collectie van fora waarop mensen dingen kunnen delen in zogenoemde 'Subreddits', is door ons een vragenlijst gedeeld in de subreddit 'r/Discordian'. Hierop hebben rond de dertig aanhangers van het Discordianisme gereageerd. Tussen deze reacties zijn een paar 'Jokers' gevonden, maar de meesten zijn erg uitgebreid. Dit valt onder Redditors wel te verwachten, omdat deze mensen vaak niet veel anders te doen hebben in hun dagelijks leven.

Doordat Reddit een platform is voor de hele wereld zijn de vragen in het Engels geformuleerd. Met het idee dat de mensen die dit onderzoek lezen ook Engels kunnen zullen de Engelse vragen en antwoorden gebruikt worden, met Nederlandse verduidelijking. De gestelde vragen gaan allemaal over de besproken religieuze beweging, Discordianisme. Hieronder staan de vragen uit het onderzoek genoteerd.

1. Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?
2. Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?
3. What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?
4. What is it like to be in this religion?
5. Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?
6. Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

Als verdere informatie, een Pope (genoemd bij vraag 6) is een aanhanger van het Discordianisme.

Na dit stuk worden alle vragen en de gegeven antwoorden hierop stuk voor stuk behandeld. De eerste vraag is door veel mensen ongeveer op dezelfde manier beantwoord. Hieruit is een van de antwoorden hieronder gekozen. Dit antwoord was erg uitgebreid.

"Discordianism is a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke. Or maybe its a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke [...]" (u/Sagasujin, Reddit. 2022)

Hieruit blijkt eigenlijk dat het, een soort van, 'Wat was er eerst, de kip of het ei?'-verhaal is. Niemand weet of het begon als een grap of als een religie.

Bij de tweede vraag werden de antwoorden iets vager. Veel antwoorden begonnen over een 'cause' die niet verbonden is met de tijd. Ook waren er mensen die het gewoon grappig vonden, deze mensen zijn later het nut van de religie gaan inzien. Hieronder wordt nog een mooi antwoord op deze vraag gepresenteerd.

"I didn't really join it so much as it clobbered me over the head. When I was reevaluating my view of reality and trying to figure out which movement best fit how I saw things, Discordianism was the winner (or loser)." (u/PopeMachineGodTitty, Reddit. 2022)

00006

Als antwoord op de derde vraag werden vaak hele filosofische antwoorden gegeven, vooral dat alles juist is, ook dingen die onjuist zijn. Ook een mooie quote is dat je geen kennis nodig hebt, maar dat veel drugs wel helpen. Hiernaast werd nog gezegd dat je niet alles serieus moet opvatten, het gaat vooral om de lol en het blij zijn. Een van de mooie filosofische antwoorden wordt hieronder voorgeschoteld.

“There's depth in the absurdity. It acts as a filter to keep rigid minds in the shallows. Be flexible enough to swim in the unknown.” (u/Michael_Trismegistus, Reddit. 2022)

Bij vraag 4 waren de antwoorden allemaal in de richting van het idee dat deze mensen het niet kunnen vergelijken met de werkelijkheden van anderen, doordat zij zelf in deze religie zijn opgenomen. Een mooi antwoord volgt.

“For me, it can be lonely. Most people laugh when I discuss Discordianism with them. Sometimes [...], but fortunately, nobody takes it too seriously. Discordianism is an eccentric collection of unorganised religion. Few actual "churches" means the community is mostly online, and almost every Discordian has slightly different views from one another.” (u/BreerEeto, Reddit. 2022)

De antwoorden op vraag 5 waren heel verwarrend totdat een van de antwoorden linkte naar de Principia Discordia (The Younger & Ravenhurst, 1980). Hierin staan, op pagina 00004, de officiële regels van het Discordianisme. Hieronder staan ze genoteerd.

I - There is no Goddess but Goddess and She is Your Goddess. There is no Erisian Movement but The Erisian Movement and it is The Erisian Movement. And every Golden Apple Corps is the beloved home of a Golden Worm.

II - A Discordian Shall Always use the Official Discordian Document Numbering System.

III - A Discordian is Required during his early Illumination to Go Off Alone & Partake Joyously of a Hot Dog on a Friday; this Devotive Ceremony to Remonstrate against the popular Paganisms of the Day: of Catholic Christendom (no meat on Friday), of Judaism (no meat of Pork), of Hindic Peoples (no meat of Beef), of Buddhists (no meat of animal), and of Discordians (no Hot Dog Buns).

IV - A Discordian shall Partake of No Hot Dog Buns, for Such was the Solace of Our Goddess when She was Confronted with The Original Snub.

V - A Discordian is Prohibited of Believing what he reads.” (The Younger & Ravenhurst, 1980)

Deze regels moeten natuurlijk met een korreltje zout genomen worden, omdat deze religie door sommigen als een grap gezien kan worden. Er is ook met een reden chaos in deze religieuze beweging, de regels zijn er dus niet om gevolgd te worden. Een goede quote als reactie op deze vraag luidt als volgt.

00007

“Wait there are rules now? That's so aneristic why the fuck would there be rules”
(u/abysmancy, Reddit. 2022)

De laatste vraag was een lastige, omdat je niet echt lid wordt van Discordianisme. Discordianisme is zo ongeorganiseerd dat je jezelf gewoon een Discordiaan vindt en dan verder gaat met je dag.

Over het communicatie gedeelte van de vraag wordt gezegd dat het internet veel wordt gebruikt, als er al communicatie is. Er is namelijk niet veel communicatie tussen Discordianen.

Uit deze antwoorden blijkt dat het lastig is om aan te duiden hoe het is om bij deze religie te horen, omdat je je niet echt toetreedt tot de religie.

Slotvraag: Waarom zijn er religies?

Als laatste vraag is het belangrijk om erachter te komen waarom er religies bestaan. Discordianisme is mogelijk ontstaan als een grap, maar niet iedereen zit dit daadwerkelijk zo. Deze keuze ligt bij het individu zelf. Iedereen heeft een ander perspectief op religie. Christenen zien hun geloof als het ware geloof, en als je het niet volgt ga je naar de hel. Ze willen daarom iedereen tot het christendom bekeren, om ze te redden. Terwijl een geloof zoals zoroastrisme niet wilt dat je ertoe bekeert; Zij vinden dat je alleen tot hun geloof kan behoren als jouw ouders al zoroastrictisch zijn. Sommige atheïsten zien geloof juist als een onnozele bedoeling. Anderen maken het punt dat atheïsme een geloof op zich is. Overal op de wereld zijn religies te vinden, elk geïsoleerd of openbare dorp, stad of staat heeft een idee over hoe wij hier op aarde zijn gekomen en waarom.

Mensen hebben religies gecreëerd om orde in het leven te brengen en om hoop te brengen. Hoop dat hun leven een hoger doel heeft, hoop dat er altijd iemand zal zijn die om ze geeft en hoop dat het uiteindelijk beter zal worden, zolang ze maar geloven.

Geloof als middel van orde is ironisch om te zeggen, in een verslag over een geloof dat uitgaat van chaos. Toch blijft het waar. Eigenlijk vinden Discordianen hun orde in de chaos die wordt gecreëerd.

Een andere reden voor het ontstaan van religies is de menselijke behoefte van gemeenschap. Mensen zijn sociale wezens, die menselijk contact nodig hebben om te overleven. Meningen kunnen de samenlevingen ordenen in verschillende groepen van mensen, maar in een religie zijn er vaste regels. Er is dus geen plaats voor eigen opvattingen. In een religieuze gemeenschap hoeft men dus niet bang te zijn voor meningsverschillen, want het enige wat telt is het woord van hun God.

Concluderend, mensen creëren religie voor hun eigen mentale gezondheid en om aan hun menselijke behoeftes te voldoen. Het vinden van orde in iemands leven is cruciaal. Religie is een construct dat exclusief menselijk is. Geen ander organisme op aarde vereerd een hypothetische God, zoals wij dat doen. Met alleen hoop en liefde als motivatie. Religie is het meest unieke en mooiste ding dat mensen ooit hebben gecreëerd.

Nawoord

In dit onderzoek hebben we Discordianisme tot op de bodem uitgepluisd. We vinden het erg interessant en vaak ook grappig. Het is een bizar geloof, met hele aparte volgelingen. Dit project heeft ons zeker weten meer inzicht gegeven over mensen met een, voor ons, ongebruikelijk geloof. Dit onderzoek heeft ons de kans gegeven om naar andere mensen te kijken dan onszelf. Dit heeft onze religieuze horizon vergroot, dit heeft ervoor gezorgd dat wij anders kijken naar mensen met andere ideeën dan dat wij hebben. Met deze nieuwe kennis begrijpen wij de wereld om ons heen beter en bekijken wij deze wereld door een nieuwe lens.

000010

Bibliografie

Cusack, C. (2013). *Discordianism*. World Religions and Spirituality Project.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313723876_Discordianism

Narizny, L. (2009). *HA HA, ONLY SERIOUS: A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF JOKE RELIGIONS*, p. 23-41.

<https://scholarsbank.uoregon.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1794/9336/Thesis%20Lauriel%20Narizny.pdf?sequence=1>

The Younger, M. & Ravenhurst, O. K. (1980). *Principia Discordia*. Boulder, CO: Paladin Press.

Vervoorn, M. (2022). *School Project About Discordianism*. Reddit.

https://www.reddit.com/r/discordian/comments/v7p9w6/school_project_about_discordianism

000011

Bijlage 1

School Project About Discordianism

r/Discordia

Hi Popes, For a school project I need to do an interview with people following the chosen religion. I have chosen Discordianism as the religion I am going to write my Paper about. I hope some of you can take the time to answer these questions for me.

1. Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?
2. Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?
3. What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?
4. What is it like to be in this religion?
5. Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?
6. Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

[28 comments](#)

[SrNormanDPlume](#)

1. Yes.
2. Yes.
3. Nothing.
4. It's like rain on your wedding day, or a free ride when you've already paid.
5. Discordians do their best to obey all important laws (e.g., gravity).
6. I don't know, dude. These people are all nuts.

[HuntingGreyFace](#)

1: neither and both... seek ye out the old lady and the young dame and ask her how many realities there are in a picture.

2: causality is not bound by time and neither is gravity for that matter. but it takes a lot of energy to keep it all spinning in your head.

3: all things are true, even the false things.

4: I use this society as a platform for teaching psychological operations and social engineering but my mental flatmate fancies himself a pope

5: you are not allowed to believe anything you read

6: to effect goals effectively (yes i just like creating them)

000012

6.5 by creating content - books hold a special place for posterity but music is something only humans dance to. Either and many others allow people to download your reality tunnel. To facilitate such connections you should curate a reality that provides outputs for you to connect to their inputs

or just start your own cabal and make shit up. you will do fine.

<https://youtu.be/Zx1fqp7ir70>

<https://youtu.be/SumDHcnCRuU>

make a reality

make a model

gotta break a model of reality to make space

Sagasujin

1: Discordianism is a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretentinf to be a joke. Or maybe its a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke pretending to be a religion pretending to be a joke. Long version short we don't think "joke" and "religion" are exclusive categories. When you're dedicated to a trickster, then joking is a holy act and when you are dedicated to jokes then worship becomes a platform for joking.

2: Because some of the teachings about chaos and order resonated with me. Also it was funny at the time.

3: Knowledge is unnecessary for becoming a Discordian. A large amount of drugs is helpful.

4: I don't know. I'm inside of this paradigm of reality so I can't tell you how another one feels. I know that I experience this reality as my life. I have no knowledge of outside non-Discordian realities to compare and contrast.

5: They're not rules. More like suggestions.

6: I don't keep in contact with other popes. We keep excommunication each other and that stops communication.

barsoap

1. Are apples fruit, or just a collection of molecules experiencing attractive forces?
2. Nothing is without cause. It's the sense part that's debatable.
3. Don't join. Or do, it makes no difference.
4. Backrubs and tickles.

000013

5. Yes.
6. You're already a subject of Our Lady no matter what so the question is pointless. Or futile, depending. As to keeping contact, we stick apart, as is ordained.

PopeMachineGodTitty

1. Discordiansim is extremely inclusive, so lots of people view Discordianism in different ways - religion, a gag, somewhere in between or all around. It's all correct.
2. I didn't really join it so much as it clobbered me over the head. When I was reevaluating my view of reality and trying to figure out which movement best fit how I saw things, Discordianism was the winner (or loser).
3. Too late. You're already a Pope.
4. It's not really like anything. It's just life as usual.
5. None. Rules are for Greyface.
6. I wouldn't join any religion. Discordianism is not organized so you just kind of consider yourself a Discordian and move on. Since everyone's a Pope, I just talk, write, type, whatever.

WalkerInDarkness

1. Only in as much as anything else that exists. Everything is a joke and none of it is. It is merely our perspective that provides the lens of what we find humour in.
2. It is something that finds you as much as you find it.
3. That the linearity of their joining is not what is happening so much as what has happened.
4. What color is the air around you?
5. Rules are meant to be questioned.
6. Discordianism is a disorganized religion.

LairdOpusFluke

The thing is The Discordian Society is obeying the rule set by Mal2 that, "We Discordians must stick apart." But, on the other hand, "a Discordian Shall not believe anything they read." On the *other* hand there's a lot of Dada behind it. On the other *other* hand if you want certainty there's plenty of other religious setups to The Big Joke. On the *other* other hand don't listen to The Bobbies as they are nuts. I think there's a foot in there too about the Fourth/Fifth Edition of the *Principia* being free online so you can read it for yourself. A limb about watching the film "They Live!". Possibly an organ advocating Zen. A bone whispers heresy about *Illuminatus!*

Sometimes it just rains.

BreerEeto

000014

1. Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?

Discordianism is definitely a religion. Sometimes, a Discordian holds multiple religious beliefs, as the simplicity of Discordianism has room to expand upon. For example, I follow Eris, but also believe in the entirety of the Greek Gods and then some. I have a fellow Pope who follows the teachings of Eris secondarily to their native heritage.

2. Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?

My mom tried to raise me as a good Anglican boy, who followed God and Jesus. Not because she herself believe it, but because it would be easier for me, where I grew up. By 9, it all sounded like Holy Nonsense, and I became an athiest, but that left me mostly unsatisfied. Sure, a spark caused the Big Bang, science guesses, but what caused a spark in nothing? When I was 13, I found Goddess. It filled in the gaps. What caused the spark of the big bang? A woman, uncontrollably giving birth to the universe. Why is there so much evil or random pain, if there is a God? Well, Eris is one of a pantheon of Gods, none of them wholly good or evil, each of them seeing life a little differently. Simple answers to questions I couldn't properly answer before came to me.

3. What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?

Don't take anything too seriously. Most of Discordianism is about having fun and being happy. Hell is up teaches that a faithful Discordian causes chaos in life because all the fun people go to Hell. This implies that there is no divine punishment for being a bad person, but a divine sorting based on who you were in life. You can be Lawful Evil as easily as Chaotic Good. So be chaotic, have fun, and be happy.

4. What is it like to be in this religion?

For me, it can be lonely. Most people laugh when I discuss Discordianism with them. Sometimes, they joke about how they finally find a God they can vibe with, but fortunately, nobody takes it too seriously. Discordianism is an eccentric collection of unorganized religion. Few actual "churches" means the community us mostly online, and almost every Discordian has slightly different views from one another.

5. Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?

Joyously partake of a hotdog on a Friday. This Devotive Ceremony to Remonstrate against the popular Paganisms of the Day: of Catholic Christendom (no meat on Friday), of Judaism (no meat of Pork), of Hindic Peoples (no meat of Beef), of Buddhists (no meat of animal), and of Discordians (no Hot Dog Buns). It circumvents even Discordian teachings, showing you how easy you should take everything. I think it's an essential rule for showing how seriously you should take the rules.

6. Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

000015

Let me answer keeping in contact first, because it's simpler and less redundant. The internet is a magical place, where groups of likeminded individuals can congregate even thousands of miles apart.

I think you should join Discordianism if the meaningless of life overwhelms you, and you have a hard time coping with the pretend realities of regular society. It has valuable lessons to teach in a relaxed way, and can feasibly answer any deeper questions of existing one feels they need.

I close with this: King Kong died for your sins, and don't believe anything you read. If you have any further questions, I would be happy to try to answer as helpfully as possible (though I could have taken the chaos route here)

[breloomancer](#)

1. there is no such distinction. it would be pretty silly to be part of a religion where you weren't having any fun
2. i read the Principia Discordia, and, though on the surface, it was a lot of nonsense, if i looked deeper, i could see that it made a lot of sense, and if i looked even deeper, i could see that it was all nonsense, which makes perfect sense
3. five tons of flax
4. Discordianism isn't really a unified religion as much as a bunch of eccentrics with their own beliefs that all call themselves discordians. i was already an eccentric before I became a discordian, so really not much has changed for me
5. the only rule of discordianism is not to tell anyone about our super secret plans to turn the earth into a hotdog. you'll keep it a secret, right?
6. us discordians tend to stick apart, but everyone is a pope, not just discordians; even the cabbages are popes! really, the hard thing is avoiding contact with popes. in a pinch, i find that a quick casting of the turkey curse is enough to make most popes think twice about approaching you

[slothrop-dad](#)

1. Yes, it's as much of a religion as any other cult proclaiming as such, except at least Discordians are fun. It also helps that Eris is pretty good looking, though not the *best* looking, as ancient lore would have it.
2. Yes. I saw an attractive girl reading the Principia Discordia on my college campus one day. I picked up a copy because the cover looked cool and I hoped to have an "in" if I ever saw her again. I never did see her again, and now I am convinced it was Eris come down to give me a divine purpose. However, what that purpose is and why she had so many piercings continue to remain a divine mystery to this day.
3. At its core, to me at least, discordianism is both a beatnik religion and an anti-religion wrapped up in a post-modern philosophy with a zany, self-aware twist. It also seems to have a strong agnostic, anti-capitalist, and anarchistic bent.

000016

4. It's fine. Sometimes the adherents can be real weirdos, it attracts a mixed bag of largely harmless and fun outcasts and goobers.
5. Do you eat hotdogs with no bun on Fridays because Eris proscribes it, or do you eat a hot dog *with* a bun on Fridays specifically because she forbids it? How many religious mores are being stamped on just by the simple act of eating a hotdog on a Friday? Truly, the world may never know.
6. You would only join if you want to, or not. You can come and go as you please. You can keep in contact with others through Reddit, Facebook, there is also a forum, and a discord. I've only met two other discordians in real life, and both occurred by chance.

CapnArrrgyle

1. Didn't you already say it was a religion? Why would you chose it if it wasn't a religion? What game are you playing?
2. Is there a movement or is the universe going by while we stand in one spot laughing at it in joy and despair?
3. What gives you the authority to ask this? Aren't you a Pope yet?
4. What are you experiencing? Is it confusing?
5. Wasn't there something about hot dogs? Or are we the folks that ignore rules for the sake of creative chaos?
6. Do any of us have a choice? Aren't I answering your questions now? Is this communicating?

zomboscott

Historiadiscordia.com is a good source for early discordian documents. Intermittents and the Black Iron Prison are more modern musings on Discordianism. I think I was supposed to tell you something about hotdog buns and the 23 enigma and the assassination of John F. Kennedy and something about reality tunnels and Power without perception being virtually useless and of no true value.

abysmancy

1. Some people claim that discordianism is a religion disguised as a joke disguised as a religion while others claim it's a joke disguised as a religion disguised as a joke.
2. Wait nobody said anything about joining anything. Do I have to join something? Cuz if I have to join something then fuck it I'm out.
3. Why would they want to do that? What's wrong with them?
4. Sometimes it's like eating a nice warm bowl of hotdog bisque although come to think of it it's really only like that when I actually am eating a nice warm bowl of hotdog bisque oh and sometimes it's like shouting at the jars of pickles in the grocery aisle.
5. Wait there are rules now? That's so aneristic why the fuck would there be rules

000017

6. ovely time skipping and frolicking in the meadow on a bre

Michael Trismegistus

1. It's a philosophy, in essence. It is the rejection of external authority and the expression of creativity.
2. I stumbled upon the Principia Discordia and saw the value in deconstructing the rules and pretenses of life in order to free my mind and increase my flexibility and creativity.
3. There's depth in the absurdity. It acts as a filter to keep rigid minds in the shallows. Be flexible enough to swim in the unknown.
4. Once you unshackle your mind, you can see the shackles on the minds of others. We call it, "seeing the fnoords."
5. <https://principiadiscordia.com/book/11.php>
6. Join because angry and miserable people tell you it's stupid. You can spot another Pope in their actions. If you see a person defying convention, they are a Pope, whether they know it or not.

Shimada Tiddy Twist

1. five
2. Tons
3. of
4. flax

BettyVonButtpants

1. Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?

Its what you make it, I made mine a boat, a terrible boat, but a boat.

2. Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?

Probably. Past me was a different person

3. What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?

That if you take yourself seriously, you fucked up.

4. What is it like to be in this religion?

I dont know, I was never in it, I'm usually in buildings or outside.

5. Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?

000018

No.

6. Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

I have a few visible tattoos, I say hi to others, otherwise, I'd like this to stay niche, get too big and the dumbasses might steal it.

PM_ME_YOUR_ROTES

1. Three pounds of flax.
2. My Wednesdays were free.
3. Everything is true.
4. Fnord
5. A Discordian shall always use the Official Discordian Document Numbering System.
6. Why would I join..? As mentioned, my Wednesdays were free. Are you even paying attention? Also, I use the internet just like everybody else.

ssttuueeyy

1. Yes
2. Seek the Goddess if you would be wise and find delight in her great surprise.
3. To be one, simply declare it
4. Fine
5. A discordian is forbidden from believing anything they read. THINK FOR YOURSELF SCHMUCK
6. Why wouldn't you? I don't, discordians are insufferable.

patch5

I'm kind of a lapsed Discordian, having not eaten a hotdog for many years, but here's my too scents:

1. Just like with every faith, it's both a religion and an excuse to screw around.
2. It spoke to me, and seemed to fit my personality without excessive chaffing: a religion that requires one to question everything, including itself, was the right religion for me.
3. I really try not to proselytize, but I think it's important for anyone joining *any* religion to understand that all religions are crap, so if you really think you need one, be sure pick one that won't make you hate looking at yourself in the mirror.
4. Apart from Tuesday mornings, it's pretty relaxed.
5. The rule of Fives is a good one. Also, one must *a/ways* use the Official Discordian Document Numbering System.

000019

6. One *might* want to join this religion after reading the work of Robert Anton Wilson, or having stumbled upon the Principia Discordia. Or because they really enjoy hot dogs, perhaps, or if they just like stirring up shit. I can't tell you how to keep in contact with other Popes, though; I can't even keep up with my family properly.

ErisZen

1. Why not both? It's a religion. I list it as my religion on forms when asked. Although, I prefer to call it "Erisian Atheism". It is also a group of people who have fun celebrating their beliefs together.
2. When I was a young, I was fooled into taking beliefs very seriously. I fell into a fundamentalist form of Christianity. Through pure chance, I stumbled across the Principia Discordia and related writings. Through reading and reflecting on what I discovered, I was saved from that folly.
3. You don't need to join. You're already a Pope. We don't run around seeking converts. We don't need people to officially join anything. If you want to join, read the Principia. Go eat a hotdog on a Friday. And stop taking stuff so seriously.
4. I am not sure what you wish to know. What is it like to be in any religion?
5. There is no governor anywhere. You are absolutely free.
6. I consider myself a Discordian because it saved me from the chains I had placed on myself. It showed me the cage that I was in was of my own design and the door wasn't locked. How do we keep in contact with other Popes? Everyone is a Pope, so each person that I meet and interact with every day is a Pope. What do I do when I meet an enlightened Pope? Someone who knows they're a Pope? I follow the old Zen master's saying, "If you meet the Buddha on the road, kill him."

fsactual

Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?

It's a religion for groups of people who do things for fun.

Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?

I would assume so, though I cannot be absolutely sure without a better understanding of how quantum physics works at the brain level.

What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?

Everything, if possible. Barring that, nothing.

What is it like to be in this religion?

It's like exploring the entire universe in an instant, then forgetting it.

Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?

000020

ALL of them. Especially the ones about not following rules.

Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

I would join this religion if it felt like something I was compelled to do, and I keep contact with the other popes by excommunicating them all so that I am the only one left, then talking to myself in the mirror.

[trillgamesh_0](#)

a discordian school project is the first episode of the wonder years when the principal tells Kevin he can't take an apple out of the cafeteria and he just lobs it across the room

R.I.P. Brian Cooper

[Autonomousdrone](#)

No true Discordian would consent to this crass mockery of writing a paper just because some so called authority has asked .Sad to see Discordianism is gone for good .

<https://youtu.be/xLrLlu6KDss>

[PeterLemonjellow](#)

1. I'd call it more of a fruit salad than anything else. Maybe - maybe - a quiche. But not for breakfast. We are not animals, after all.
2. No.
3. They should know literally everything before joining. I'm being 100% serious in this answer. You need to know literally everything relevant to Discordianism before joining.
4. You know that feeling when you really have to pee, and then that feeling immediately after when you have just peed? It's like the second feeling.
5. All of them.

6.a - The tax benefits

6.b - Our pineal glands.

[fubo](#)

1. It's an evolving parareligious metasigil taking the form of a silly joke.
2. Joined it? I was just hangin' out and *it* joined *me*!
3. Sorry, you're too late (which is better than tool ate; eating tools is bad for your teeth). You already are several bodily members of Discordianism.
4. Burritos become subtly tastier as a sign of the Goddess's yumminess.

000021

5. No matter what you do, **do not** follow this rule.¹
 6. Love is all you need. Well, that and burritos. Burritos is nice.
-

¹ Exceptions eternally? Absolute cheese!

Oflameo

1. Yes
2. I wished someone trained me to think like a sociopath, and that put me on Eris's radar.
3. Join Neopaganism instead.
4. It was okay, but too much spiritual power was left on the table. The cultural sense of the word, atheists. I don't believe in super nature.
5. Discordians do their best to obey all important laws (e.g., gravity).
6. I keep in contact with other popes on here and Erischan. You would join Discordianism or Neopaganism if you are crazy enough to work with Eris or her associates. Working on making more spaces. Barely anything in Meetspace around here, but I think Jack Chick may be able to fix that.

vimefer

Is Discordianism a religion, or is it just a group of people who do it for fun?

Yes. Think of the famous "[Poe's Law](#)", and apply it unironically to any religious movement. You will inevitably conclude that there is no criterium for distinguishing between a "real religion" and a parody cult. That is because, by their very own metaphysical nature, they are the same thing. All religion is bullshit, it's a feature of religions: the very act of religious belief is belief in what is necessarily unprovable and/or unfathomable and/or nonsensical.

Anything else is merely a kinky subset of science at its core.

Therefore, Discordianism is the truest, realest and most genuine religion of all: it is the one faith that embraces 100% its very own metaphysical nature. Everyone else is just in denial.

Is there a reason you joined this religious movement?

Yes, I was visited personally by the Goddess when I was 23. This was an intense religious experience, [comparable to those documented in the medical literature](#). It cured me of my years of suicidal depression and set me on a long successful path of personal improvement. I am now an officially ordained minister (for the sole purpose of shooing the local authorities away when necessary, and potentially celebrating legally-binding marriage in the future), I stand secure in my understanding that the Goddess loves me just like She loves all of us

000022

infinitely. That's why She messes with us constantly and we only need abide Her and acknowledge Her voice. I speak to Her and She answers. It's totally not schizophrenia, I swear.

What should someone know about discordianism, if they want to join?

We have no membership card, no official list, no mandatory dogma, that is the entire point of it. You decide whether you are Discordian, simply by calling your beliefs such. You might even already be one of us but simply unaware of that fact !

What is it like to be in this religion?

It feels very much like starring in an improvised live-action episode of the Animaniacs.

Which rules do you need to follow in this religion?

The point of Discordianism is that we deny rules in religious matters. We do not have dogma, we actively oppose having any kind of dogma, which we are free to (but not obliged in any way) to replace with catma instead.

You may hear some Discordians refer to the PentaBarf, as a set of 5 rules all Discordians ought to follow, but those are really only "rules" we made up in order to break them. You could even think that the practice of Discordianism itself is the breaking or otherwise flouting of rules, but even that is an oversimplification that risks missing the point.

Why would you join this religion and how do you keep contact with other Popes?

You would embrace Discordianism because, as explained above, it is ultimately the truest religion. It's where you end up by simply working away at your beliefs and shedding your denial.

Any communication method is valid to keep up with each other. We here contribute our zany stories and random post-hoc-sed-ante thoughts with others on this subreddit, because it is most convenient. Telepathy and over-interpretation of global news also serve for coordination, especially when done under the influence.

There are also electronic publications (newsletters, magazines, blogs), real-life events in the more densely occupied areas, and simple ways to publicize your Discordianism around you such as catchphrases, quotes and other hand gestures - which I will not detail here for privacy reasons.

